

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH

EFFECTS OF LEGAL TERRORISM ON MEN'S HEALTH

TRUTH IS OUT HERE

AUTHOR: RUDOLPH D'SOUZA

Co-author: Hiren Parikh

Date: 13/March/2021

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

Summary: Study on Men's Health covers a broad range of research on men's health and wellbeing. What causes men to die young? How do false cases which Supreme Court of India has called "legal terrorism", daily abuse and harassment by women against her male partner by using "women centric" laws in India effect men's mental health and overall health. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of men who are neglected by international organizations as well as government bodies within India.

The exact numbers of such cases are difficult to assess as majority cases go unreported. It is even tougher to figure out with exactitude how many men are suffering because of "legal terrorism"!

Key Findings: Majority men feel shy to come forward to report abuse, harassment, misuse of law and so most men suffer in silence and die young. There are no support groups to help men. None of the study reports or details highlighting atrocities on men are acknowledged by any institute, government body, and the mainstream media is reluctant to publish abuse on men or health issues concerning men in particular.

Methodology: Information for this report is sourced from various secondary sources, medical journals and various news publications, testimonies, survey statistics etc.

Introduction: Analysis report on Study on Men's Health address following questions: How men are harassed? How legal terrorism is impacting their health? How do they suffer in silence? Why do they suffer in silence? How stressful life they lead, when they face abuse and humiliation at the hands of their beloved ones. Most of the literature collected by MyNation demonstrates that there is a dearth of research on men's mental health or overall health when someone is reported to be depressed due to marital distress or stressful relationship. There is no government body or agency for men in distress to consult with, no funding earmarked to encourage any organization (governmental or non-governmental) to work for men's health issues or address their socio-economic problems or to support men in distress. This study article / report is based on review of literature obtained from legal journals, medical journals and reference from other study reports.

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

Psychological research has found that relationships have "direct influences" on physiological, immune, neurosensory, and other cardiovascular mechanisms. So, bad relationship leads to depression and stress in people. According to the American Psychological Association, men aren't reporting emotional and physical symptoms of stress because of societal pressure and hence men try to hide their stress and suffer in silence.

A simple online search for "depression due to toxic relationships", leads to hundreds of articles only on women. Most of the readers and writers are women and they are very good in glorifying problems of women alone and showcasing as if men are immune to depression or stress. Very Few research or articles are available on addressing the alarming issue of men's health. The present study aims to highlight this gap in research.

What Is Stress?

Stress is the human body's reaction to unhealthy, painful damaging situations. When a person feels threatened, a chemical reaction occurs in their body that allows them to act in a way to prevent damaging injury psychologically or physically. As a response or reaction to stress, breathing quickens, muscles tighten, heart rate increases and blood pressure (BP) rises.

Stress doesn't discriminate anyone. While mostly similar stress symptoms are experienced by men and women both, there are a few that are exclusive or more common in men. Stress can affect anyone at any time, regardless of sex. And it all depends on how we manage stress which differs between men and women. Some handle any stress better than others. Not all type of stress is bad. In small doses, stress can help you accomplish tasks and prevent you from getting hurt and stop you from drifting to depression. It is said that when relationship fails, men take it to heart and corner themselves or withdraw from the society.

Evidence suggests that women handle stress better than men, whereas men are most likely to succumb to major depression brought in by family related and financial issues. Men are also more likely to withdraw from society while dealing with stressful relationships. Studies have also shown that stressful relationships are leading cause of psychological impotence and ill health. There are numerous causes of stress in romantic relationships, married or otherwise. When couples are constantly under pressure to fulfil their duties and

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

roles, the relationship could be at risk of failure. The stress men experience from these relationships can affect their physical as well as mental health.

Men's bodies are designed to handle small doses of stress or short term shocks. But they are not equipped to handle long-term, prolonged chronic stress without proper attention leading to deadly consequences.

Ongoing chronic, prolonged stress, can cause many serious health problems including:

1. Mental health problems such as depression, anxiety, behavioral problems, being pessimistic, poor judgment, forgetfulness & disorganization, inability to focus, personality disorders, nervousness, shaking, getting easily agitated, frustrated, and moody.
2. Physical health problems like cardiovascular disease, including chronic heart disease, chest pain and rapid heartbeat, high blood pressure, abnormal heart rhythms, heart attacks, Headaches, stroke, insomnia, diarrhea, constipation, nausea, aches, pains, tense muscle, obesity and other eating disorders
3. Sexual dysfunction such as impotence and premature ejaculation in men and loss of sexual desire in men
4. Skin and hair problems such as acne, psoriasis, and eczema, premature greying of hair, and permanent hair loss

Signs and Symptoms of stress in men

Stress in men can manifest as psychological signs like depression, anxiety, anger, sadness and restlessness; behavioral changes like less sleep or over sleeping, drugs or alcohol abuse in order to forget events of stress, overeating or under eating, isolating oneself, social withdrawal, excessive smoking, carelessness or compulsive behaviors and physical signs like muscle tension, chest pain or body pain, lack of interest in sex or achieving or maintaining an erection, rapid heartbeats, fatigue and difficulty in concentrating.

Evidence suggests that people in toxic relationships or with an abusive wife who filed false cases to harass men, are three times as likely to experience depression as compared to others. Unhappy or broken marriage relationships are a risk factor for depression. Some studies have found that over 60% of those with depression consider relationship problems to be the main cause of their illness.

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

Main Causes for Depression in Indian men.

Stress leads to depression. Stress from family or relationships is the main cause for depression among men.

Strained relationship or broken marriage: Many articles can be found which supports the theory of depression leading to divorce, without assessing why men are depressed? For a woman, marriage is protective against depression. Many women who were depressed pre-marriage, get someone to blame for their situation. Women are comparatively less depressed than men and it is akin to hitting the jackpot when they are granted a dole of maintenance by the court while going through divorce process. Many men are forced to live together with an abusive spouse for the sake of children, inability to pay unrealistic maintenance or alimony demands made by wife, for the sake of family reputation or some other personal reasons. Wife's nagging and finding fault in every aspect of life reduces his performance at work and his zeal for participation in other socio-economic and cultural activities. In India most live together as a joint family, but lately as soon as they marry the wife forces the man to separate from his family and keep distance from his aged parents. There are even news reports with instances where a son was forced by the wife to kick out his parents. Isolating a man from his parents is the first sign of future abuse by the wife. Men are adjusting with an abusive wife because of his children. Indian law system is biased towards men and so she can take away the children and prevent the man from meeting them by just filing a domestic violence case misusing the provision of "protection order" available at her disposal in the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 which fails to recognize 'men' as a 'victim' of domestic violence. Even if the wife is abusive or tortures her husband and in-laws, the man has no option to file a case or report to the police or court.

False accusations and false cases: In India every word of a woman is Gospel truth, for society or legal system, she is treated as Abla nari ie, innocent and a victim. She can accuse anyone, harass or kill and get away with it (Ref: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4445147> - *Violence Against Men – False Accusation of Sexual Harassment* and <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819> - *CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN*) there are many reports of false accusations of rape, outraging modesty of women, false cases like dowry demand and domestic violence. These cases and accusations not only push men to depression but many also commit suicide because of depression and stress. Even if men who survive the long legal battle are acquitted of any such false accusations, regaining their

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

pride and status in the conservative Indian society is very difficult. This in turn leads them to deep depression and forces them to take drastic step of committing suicide.

How Depression / Stress affects men's health

Stress / Depression can actually make you sick and disturb peace of mind. A national study reported that 60 to 80 percent of doctor's visits may have a stress-related component. Stress has also been linked to a higher risk for disease, including cardiovascular disease, neurological imbalance and certain cancers.

The following are problems and complications of stress and how they affect men's health.

Cardiovascular disease

All types of stress have shown to increase the risk of heart related issues and disease. Researchers have found that stressed people have a higher risk of high blood pressure and heart problems. Stress can directly increase blood flow, heart rate and causes the release of cholesterol and triglycerides into the bloodstream. Stress increases blood pressure and cholesterol, which are the major risk factors in the development of heart disease. Repeated and prolonged events of stress also cause inflammation in the coronary arteries, increasing the risk for a heart attack.

Male infertility

Testosterone levels will reduce because chronic stress on men result in loss of libido or reduced sex drive. Sperm production, and sperm quality increases the risk of infertility. Chronic prolonged stress also impairs testosterone production which can cause impotence.

Prostate cancer

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

A study found that stress on nervous system promotes tumor growth and spread and ultimately increases the risk of prostate cancer. Sympathetic nervous system (SNS) regulates the body's immune system to fight-or-flight response to depression because of stress. Stress causes SNS to release the chemical noradrenaline, which was found to trigger a cancer-stimulating response. Parasympathetic nervous system (PNS) nerve fibers release another chemical that helps cancer cells break away and spread to other parts of the body.

Erectile dysfunction

Depression because of Stress can cause erectile dysfunction(ED) in men, and relationship stress is the leading cause of ED in middle-aged men. Abuse and humiliation lower performance in bed by the partner further leading to stress and strain in the relationship. Stress affects the brain signals to the penis that reduces the blood flow needed for an erection.

Emotional effects of stress combined with stress and anxiety about erectile dysfunction also contributes to an ongoing cycle of ED.

Obesity.

Stress causes higher levels of the hormone cortisol, which store excess fat in the belly which pose greater health risks than fat on the legs or hips and turn person more obese

Diabetes.

Stress can worsen diabetes, also raise the glucose levels of people with type 2 diabetes directly.

Social and Other health issues

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

Most men with prolonged events of stress withdraw from society, they isolate themselves and fall into depression. Ongoing stress can create severe problems on your gastrointestinal system. Even brief episodes of stress can cause stomach upset and pain, chronic pain, chronic constipation, stomach ulcers, diarrhea and heartburn

Stress is also a common cause of headache and trigger for migraine. Stress causes muscles to tense, which can lead to ongoing pain in your whole body or neck, back and shoulders. Numbness in touch or bottom of the foot or has been linked to increased pain sensitivity too. Living with chronic pain also increases your stress and anxiety which leads to depression.

Abuse, control and 'power play' in the relationship, results in toxic relationships or broken marriage making it a reason for stress which leads to depression. In India most of the time women separate children from fathers and our legal system stands biased against men, with inherent prejudice they term all men as 'permanent potential abuser and child molester'. A simple online search for the phrase "all men are rapist" will fetch a plenty of "feminist" articles and quotes spreading this prejudiced misinformation. As per statistics of Indian judiciary only 2% fathers get custody of their children and 5% fathers get visitation rights and rest all only have to keep paying maintenance that leads to emotional problems (depression, anxiety, anger, grief, guilt, low self-esteem) resulting from parental-child alienation.

Most of the Indian women are control freak and after recent law reforms women has one sided laws in favor of them that make them empowered to abuse their husband and that leads to less interest in Intimacy and no sex marriage which is another cause for health problems, if your partner is thinking about or marriage is on the brink of divorce, many men take refuge of alcohol or start using drugs. The signs of stress related to personal relationships are similar to normal symptoms of general stress and may include physical health and sleep problems, depression, and anxiety. For men, losing a child is the deadliest stress, they suffer silently and suffer from inside thinking about children. This stress comes from inside, rather than outside. You can stress yourself out just by worrying or thinking about problems or things. All of these factors can lead to more stress, depression and ultimately drive men to grave.

Such men unless counseled and treated for such drastic situation, start to lose hair, turn obsess, neglect themselves, loose interest in keeping themselves fit and fall sick now and then in cyclic manner. They perform poorly at work and many times lost job and go bankrupt coz they are forced to pay child maintenance without allowing him to meet his

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

children. In Indian judicial system there is no mechanism nor all law to share child access equally. Indian laws designed only for women in child custody matters, mother take the child custody by default. Even though law book says that father is a natural guardian, but that is only in law books seem to be there only with a purpose to shed out money from his pocket in absence of any provision for default 50-50% custody. Custody Judgments statistics says 95% mother are getting custody, because it is one more way to hand over the dole of maintenance in the hands of woman “in the name of child’s maintenance” while at the same time excluding the man from the company of the child..

When you are passing through a stressful situation, your body launches a physical response, that’s called a stress system. When your nervous system springs into action, the stress system releases hormones that prepare the body and mind to fight the stress, when you're in a stressful situation, you may notice that your breathing gets faster, your muscles tense, your heartbeat speeds up, and you start to sweat. This kind of stress is temporary and short-term (acute stress), and your body usually recovers quickly from it.

But if your stress system stays activated over a prolonged period which is also called chronic stress, it can lead to or aggravate more serious health issues and problems. The constant rush of stress hormones can create problems and put a lot of wear and tear on your body, causing it to age more quickly and making it more prone to illness and early death. Stress can affect all aspects of your life, including your emotions, behaviors, thinking ability, and physical health resulting in low self-esteem and poor performance in day to day life. No part of the body is immune.

What is LEGAL TERRORISM how it will affect Men’s Health.

WHAT IS LEGAL TERRORISM?

A harassment by the legitimized agency of the state with the help of laws as a tool, channelized through judicial court or police by vexatious litigation, or by the individuals or unscrupulous persons to wreak personal vendetta or unleash harassment by filing of lawsuits to extort money/ assets or force to admit for their demands is “legal terrorism”.

In India, for a woman, the best way to harass her husband to get divorce or maintenance is filing false cases against his aged parents along with him. Even though they never stayed

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

with them or are staying far away, police will add their name by default. It all depends on how the police have been bribed with and how influential the women's family is. Police even include brothers/sisters even breast fed 2/3 months old child of husband sisters have been included in many reports.

In India, it is very easy for a woman to file a complaint with police. Anyone can go to the police station, shed some crocodile tears, cry loudly and police are bound to register her complaint without verifying any of her claim or evidence. Height of all! Some claimed to be raped by a person who was miles away in another city or even if she claims she was raped in her dream. Police will register her complaint and start arresting whoever she names.

False case of matrimonial issue which not only is enough to tarnish the image of a familial man, or person, or a family in the eyes of the society but often drive people to other extreme measure as harming themselves, creating depression and even driving many to end their precious God given life.

(Ref: **Police Atrocities in Legal Terrorism** - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4519381>)

Men are always neglected by international organizations and government bodies. None of the survey data study institutes or media is not ready to publish domestic violence/abuse experienced by men or their mental health resulting from such abuse.

According to the research, 40 per cent of Indian wives admitted to having had an intimate relationship outside their marriage (Ref: <https://supari.org/40-percent>) she can have sex in front of her husband at his home, but he cannot do anything legally as Section 497 IPC scrapped by Indian judiciary. Value system of the Indian society, founded on 'truth and non-violence' has already been tossed in the name of clash between 'morality' v/s 'liberty' (absolute) and 'justice' (gendered). While constitutional legality is being talked about, the constitutional ethics and constitutional morality has completely been forgotten. Thereby making us think, whether the makers of a lengthy Modern Indian Constitution and the Modern India desired an 'adulterous future' for its citizens, while penning down the 'equality and liberty' along with 'fraternity' among its citizens? Whether polygamy/polyandry or adultery will lead to retention or disruption of 'peace and fraternity'? It needs to be well thought about by the legislature and judiciary.

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

Today, legally any woman can file a case on man and all her allegations are assumed "possible" as they stayed under one roof and closed walls. These baseless allegations can be shattered through proper investigation, but India has investigation officers and protection officers who do not even know the basics of the complaint verification process. There are scenarios, where the bride has come back after a year of eloping with someone, but the groom's family had spent that one year in jail on charges of bride's murder. Corruption also plays a major role in the misuse of these gender biased laws.

The latest health statistics paint a grim picture of India's mental health of men revealing that one person commits suicide every four minutes. The National Health Profile 2018 raises alarm over the increasing numbers of suicide deaths-a whopping 1, 33,623 in a year.

This translates into 366 suicide deaths every day and 15 an hour.

The following data also show increasing vulnerability of Indian men vis-à-vis women.

Nearly 70 per cent of all suicide deaths in India involve males. Of the 1, 33,623 people who killed themselves, 68.49 per cent (91,528) were men as against 42,088 women.

The number of suicides by men has risen from 66,032 in 2000 and 80,544 in 2008 to 91,528 currently. The number of male deaths from suicides is nearly double than that of females.

According to the latest data, the highest suicide burden is in Maharashtra (16,970 deaths), followed by Tamil Nadu (15,777) and Bengal (14,602).

Health data also reveal that suicides are the highest in the productive age group of 30 to 45.

Data from the Survey show that men made up about 45% of Domestic Violence victims each year between 2018-19 and last year for which figures are unavailable. In 2016-17 men made up 43.4% of all those who had suffered partner abuse in the previous year, which rose to 45.5% in 2017-18.

Violence on men can range from anything like - physical violence including slapping, pushing, hitting by wife, her parents and her relatives; emotional violence with wife threatening suicide to intimidate and control the husband; verbal abuse if husband remains in contact with his parents or comes home late from work; throwing objects like utensils, mobile phones and crockery at the husband; sexual abuse if husband denies sex to mental abuse by constant threats of implicating the husband and his family under false case of dowry and domestic violence.

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

(Ref: **Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health** - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4431600>)

Above article talks in detail about abuse of men by his partner/wife but there is not a single survey conducted by the Indian government or any other organization which would capture exact data on male abuse in domestic relationships. There are more and more men who are being pushed to suicide because of strain in marriage and abuse by wife. Suicidal tendencies do not come to men by birth, it's because of stress men face at home and outside which push them to such extremes. When there is no helping hand available then they have no choice for them.

Psychological Impact on MEN Due to Biased Women Centric Laws

In India MEN Are presumed to be guilty until proven innocent. And based on verbal complaint to police, innocent man & his entire family gets arrested.

Once the false complaint is filed; all relatives, friends, neighbors, acquaintances and other known people immediately cut-off relationship with such accused MEN & their family members who are involved in such false cases. Once trapped in these fake cases, it becomes a social taboo which assumes that "all accused are criminals". Therefore in a society no one wants to keep a contact with such people. Hence Indian criminal justice system & society's prejudice against accused MEN create immense trauma & mental abuse to them.

Implicating MEN in False cases (Legal Terrorism) is enough for social Ostracization which create tremendous depression among MEN

Office employees/colleagues, managers or even subordinates stops respecting such people as soon as they come to know about false cases/proceeding against these MEN. Their professional growth such as promotion, salary increment is completely stalled or seriously affected since employers start perceiving and treating such employees in an extremely prejudice & biased way. This negative environment & behavior would directly affect to MEN's health, wellbeing, productivity & efficiency.

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

In this immense and cut-throat competitive job market, No company would like to keep any person in a job who is involved in such criminal cases (even they are not proven) – Hence the resultant impact of such legal terrorism forces MEN to commit suicide or take other drastic steps including various addiction, abuse their own health through drugs, alcohol, smoking etc.

From police stations to lawyers everyone will squeeze them financially. In order to do so police in connivance with cunning women arrest MEN, ill-treat and mentally torture them through their vast legal power.

MEN live in constant fear of losing their jobs i.e livelihood, frightened of being arrested, horrified that any time their family members may be harassed, tortured and incarcerated. MEN are at the mercy of unscrupulous Indian Women who filed false cases which is nothing but MEN becoming slave of Legal Terrorism Mafia (Women, Police, Biased Laws, Judiciary, Women Cell, Media & other Feminists organizations/NGOs). These innocent MEN are tortured by police in Jail so that they would give up the legal extortion demand by false accuser women. Hence This kind of treatment not only affect MEN's health & mental state but it also impacts then physically & mentally.

MEN & their family will have permanent seal of “criminal character” stamped on their life. Even if they are acquitted by court. Their life's previous years get wasted. They have to live their life with this social taboo being treated as criminal. This kind of treatment to MEN is nothing but the psychological, emotional, mental & economical abuse

When there are various schemes / support and funding for women why nothing for men?

Can anyone show us, like PINK RIBBON or whatever color ribbons planned for women and similar for men?

Can someone show us support and funding for reproductive health of men, men's prostate cancer or any other cancer like cervical cancer or breast cancer, reproductive health, maternal health etc. programs earmarked for women?

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

There is so much support for #MeToo Why not one for #MenToo?

Why all law support / free legal-aid services only women, why not similar laws for #MenToo?

In India men are neither allowed to talk about their problems nor they can officially report it anywhere. For stressed men there is only one option that's ending his 'dear life'. Indian government and gender biased organizations like Ministry of Women and Child Development (WCD) / National Commission for Women (NCW) by encouraging legal terrorism are further contribution to each and every suicide which Indian men are committing.

Reference:

Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4431600>

Police Atrocities in Legal Terrorism - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4519381>

40% of Indian married women have regular Sexual intercourse with Lovers outside marriage - <https://supari.org/40-percent>

Violence Against Men – False Accusation of Sexual Harassment - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4445147>

CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819>

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

Declaration: The author/s declare that there are no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article nor are they affiliated with any Political Parties or Religious organizations.

Funding: The author/s have received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article. This research study is self-funded by the authors.

Disclaimer: This Research study does not use any Fake statistics to justify any views expressed by the authors, Most Statistics used can be found on NCRB, respective Government Ministry websites or on medico legal Journals.

MyNation Hope Foundation (INDIA)

Reg: S/1934/2018

Address: 133A, Pocket-C, Siddhartha Extn. New Delhi - 110014.

Phone: +91-9972718212